
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 15

Computing level populations

Version 1.0, 22 May 2023, Peter Young

1 Overview

The calculation of level populations of an ion is perhaps the single most important part of CHIANTI. This document describes the software and methods used to perform the calculation within IDL.

Most users are recommended to use the routine `ch_pops` (Sect. 4) for calculating the populations.

2 The population equations

Each ion in CHIANTI has a discrete number of atomic levels that are labeled with integers, beginning with 1 for the ground level (see the CHIANTI `elvlc` file, described in CHIANTI Technical Report No. 1). Atomic processes such as radiative decay and electron excitation result in a transfer of population between the atomic levels. We define α_{ij} to be the rate at which population is transferred from level i to j , and N_i is the population of level i . The sum over all levels gives the population of the emitting ion within the plasma. CHIANTI assumes the plasma is in equilibrium, and thus we have

$$N_i \sum_{j \neq i} \alpha_{ji} = \sum_{j \neq i} N_j \alpha_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where the left-hand side gives rate of population transfer out of level i and the right-hand side gives the rate of population transfer into level i from all the other levels.

The diagonal elements of α are zero (population is not transferred from the level to itself), so we can define $\alpha_{ii} = -\sum_j \alpha_{ji}$, giving

$$\sum_j N_j \alpha_{ij} = 0 \quad (2)$$

It can be seen that, for a solution N^* to these equations, kN^* will also be a solution for any scalar k . It is thus necessary to specify a normalization condition and for CHIANTI we set $n_i = N_i/N_1$, i.e., the population of the ground level is fixed to one. The equations then become

$$\sum_j n_j \alpha_{ij} = b_i \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha_{11} = 1$, $\alpha_{1j} = 0$ ($j > 1$), $b_1 = 1$, and $b_j = 0$ ($j > 1$).

In the simple case of a two-level ion model with a radiative decay rate A_{21} and an electron excitation rate $N_e q_{12}$ and de-excitation rate $N_e q_{21}$, the equations are:

$$n_1 = 1 \quad (4)$$

$$n_1 N_e q_{12} - n_2 (N_e q_{21} + A_{21}) = 0 \quad (5)$$

After the matrix equation has been solved, a second normalization is applied such that $n_i^* = n_i / \sum_i n_i$, i.e., the sum of the populations is set to 1. It is this population array that is returned by the CHIANTI software.

For IDL matrices, the array `alpha[i,*]` gives the rates out of level i to all other levels and so is equivalent to α_{*i} above.

3 The pop_solver routine

The workhorse of the CHIANTI IDL software is `pop_solver`, which takes the atomic data, creates the population process array, and then performs the matrix inversion to yield the level populations.

There is a two-step process in calling `pop_solver`. For example,

```
IDL> input=ch_setup_ion('o_6')
IDL> pop_solver, input, 5e5, 1e9, pop
```

The first call loads the atomic data for the ion O VI into the structure `input`. The call to `pop_solver` then uses the atomic data to compute the populations (`pop`) at the specified temperature (5×10^5 K) and electron number density (10^9 cm⁻³).

The output `pop` is simply an array of populations for all of the ion's levels. If you need information on the identification of the levels, then you are recommended to use the routine `ch_pops` instead (Section 4).

The routine `ch_setup_ion` has a number of different options which can switch off certain processes, or modify data. Section 5 summarizes these options.

As of CHIANTI 9, new routines were added that take the atomic data from `input` and reformat them into rate matrices that form the matrix solved by `pop_solver`. More details of these “load rates” routines are given in Appendix B.

4 The ch_pops routine

A more user-friendly way of obtaining the level populations is to use the routine `ch_pops.pro`. For example:

```
IDL> pop=ch_pops('fe_13')
```

This prints the populations of the most populous levels to the screen, while information for all levels is output to the `pop` structure. The tags of the output are:

DENS	DOUBLE	1.0000000e+10
TEMP	DOUBLE	1778279.4
LEVEL	STRUCT	-> <Anonymous> Array[749]
RADTEMP	FLOAT	-1.00000
RPHOT	FLOAT	-1.00000
PROTON	STRING	'yes'
VERSION	STRING	'CHIANTI 8.0.2'
DATE	STRING	'Wed Jun 28 15:36:26 2017'
SUM_MWL	INT	0
SUM_MWL_COEFFS	FLOAT	-1.00000

The tag `level` is a structure array, with the tags:

INDEX	INT	1
TERM	STRING	'3s2 3p2 3P0'
POP	DOUBLE	0.11817674

The level population is given in the tag `pop` and it is given as the population relative to the population of the ion as a whole, so summing the `pop` values over all levels gives 1.

By default, populations are calculated at an electron number density, N_e , of 10^{10} cm^{-3} and the T_{max} of the ion (computed with `ch_tmax`) is used for the temperature. Keywords exist to switch off proton rates (`/noprot`) and level-resolved ionization and recombination rates (`/noionrec`) where these are available for the ion. Photon excitation and non-Maxwellian distributions can be included using the standard CHIANTI keywords (see CHIANTI User Guide).

Note that `ch_pops` is a wrapper for the older routine `show_pops`, which is itself a wrapper for calling `pop_solver`. `ch_pops` was written to standardize the input notation with other CHIANTI routines.

5 Atomic data setup (`ch_setup_ion`)

The default call to `ch_setup_ion` results in all of the ion's data files being loaded into the output structure. The core data-sets of energy levels, A -values, and electron collision strengths are always loaded. The secondary data-sets of proton rates and level-resolved ionization and recombination rates are loaded as long as the data files exist for the ions. They can be switched off using the `/NOPROT` and `/NOIONREC` keywords, respectively.

Photon excitation (and stimulated emission) do not have atomic data files since the rates depend on the A -values. They are switched on by the user by specifying `RPHOT`, the distance from the emitting source center in source radius units. The blackbody radiation temperature is set with the input `RADTEMP`.

For proton rates, `pop_solver` needs to know the proton density. This is computed self-consistently from the electron temperature (assumed to be the same as the proton temperature), and ion fraction file and the element abundance file. The optional inputs `IONEQ_FILE` and `ABUND_FILE` are used to specify these files. If not set, then the default files `!IONEQ_FILE` and `!ABUND_FILE` are used.

The simple call given in Sect. 3 will be sufficient for most users, but if you are calling `ch_setup_ion` from within another code and want to give users full access to the options, then the call would be:

```
input=ch_setup_ion(name,rphot=rphot,radtemp=radtemp,noprot=noprot, $
                  ioneq_file=ioneq_file,abund_file=abund_file, $
                  noionrec=noionrec)
```

6 Solving the matrix equations with IDL

The matrix equations are solved in the IDL routine `matrix_solver.pro`, which is called by `pop_solver.pro`. If we write the equations from Section 2 as $Ax = b$ (A is a 2D array, and x and b are 1D arrays), then the code is:

```
a_ludc=a
la_ludc,a_ludc,ind,/double
x=la_lusol(a_ludc,ind,b,/double)
```

This procedure was introduced in CHIANTI 10.1. Prior to this version, the built-in IDL routine `invert.pro` was used to invert A , and then $x = A^{-1}b$. With IDL 8.8.1, the routine `invert.pro` was modified so that it called `la_invert.pro` (another built-in routine). This routine was found to generate negative level populations in some cases, hence the CHIANTI software was modified to use the procedure given above.

To test the new procedure, comparisons of CHIANTI 10.0.2 atomic model level populations generated with IDL 8.7.3 (prior to the change to `invert.pro`), and with the updated procedure were performed. All ions in the database were used, and populations calculated at the T_{\max} of the ion and at 10^4 K were considered. The latter was chosen as rates can be very small at this temperature, and numerical errors are more likely. Agreement to within 0.01% was found for all ions, all levels and both temperatures, except for Cr XIV. For this ion, level 47 was found to be discrepant by 0.045% at 10^4 K. The population of this level is 1.1×10^{-320} at this temperature, however, and so it is not physically significant.

A consequence of switching from `invert.pro` to the `la_lusol` routine, is that the computation time is reduced by about a factor five.

A Document history

Version 1.0, 22-May-2023. Added Sects. 2 and 6; document moved to Overleaf.

Version 0.4, 5-Mar-2019. Added Sect. B.

B The “load rates” routines

With CHIANTI 9, a significant update to the IDL software was made. Two routines that were added are `ch_load_ion_rates` and `ch_load_2ion_rates`. These routines essentially take the atomic data that was read by `ch_setup_ion` and then reformat them into atomic rates that enter into the matrix equation that is solved by `pop_solver`. Previously this part of the code was contained in `pop_solver` itself. Now `pop_solver` calls out to the load rate routines.

Generally users will not need to run the load rates routines, but here we summarize how they work.

For most ions, the procedure is simply:

```
IDL> t=[1e5,2e5,3e5]
IDL> rates=ch_load_ion_rates('o_4',t)
```

where “t” is the temperature array for which the rates are computed. The result is a structure with the following tags:

N_LEVELS	LONG	204
AA	DOUBLE	Array[204, 204]
AAX	DOUBLE	Array[204, 204]
PPR	DOUBLE	Array[3, 204, 204]
QQ	DOUBLE	Array[3, 204, 204]
TEMP	FLOAT	Array[3]
ION_DATA	STRUCT	-> <Anonymous> Array[1]
MULT	FLOAT	Array[204]
SUM_MWL_COEFFS	DOUBLE	Array[3]
SUMTST	INT	0

The rate matrices are: radiative decay rates (AA), photoexcitation and stimulated emission rates (AAX), proton rate coefficients (PPR), and electron rate coefficients (QQ). The ION_DATA structure is simply the atomic data structure returned by `ch_setup_ion`.

If `pop_solver` sees that the tag `ion_data.autostr` exists, then it means that the ion has autoionization data (i.e., the `.auto` file exists). This requires a special two-ion atomic model whereby the CHIANTI model for the next ionization stage is added to the ion model. An example of how this is done for O VI is as follows:

```
IDL> rates1=ch_load_ion_rates('o_6',t)
IDL> rates2=ch_load_ion_rates('o_7',t)
IDL> rates=ch_load_2ion_rates(rates1,rates2)
```

The structure `rates` is then used for creating the atomic rates matrix used by `pop_solver`. Note that this structure has an expanded set of tags:

<code>N_LEVELS</code>	<code>LONG</code>	<code>972</code>
<code>AA</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[972, 972]</code>
<code>QQ</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>
<code>AAX</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[972, 972]</code>
<code>PPR</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>
<code>IONIZ</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>
<code>RR</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>
<code>AI</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[972, 972]</code>
<code>DC</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>
<code>DR</code>	<code>DOUBLE</code>	<code>Array[3, 972, 972]</code>

In particular: level-resolved ionization rate coefficients (`IONIZ`), level-resolved radiative recombination rate coefficients (`RR`), autoionization rates (`AI`), dielectronic capture rate coefficients (`DC`), and level-resolved dielectronic recombination rate coefficients (`DR`). As of CHIANTI 9, the `IONIZ` and `DR` matrices only contain data for transitions between the two ground states.

If you compare the `rates1` and `rates` structures then you will see they have 923 and 972 levels, respectively (as of CHIANTI 9). This is because the 49 levels of the O VII CHIANTI model have been added to the O VI model. The level populations are calculated by `pop_solver` for all 972 levels, but the array is then truncated to 923 levels so that only the O VI populations are returned. If you would like to see the populations for all 972 levels, then use the `/all_levels` keyword input to `pop_solver`.